

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN UZBEKISTAN**Dushatova Shohsanam Baxtiyor qizi***Fergana State University, EFL teacher, sh.dushatova@pf.fdu.uz***Mahmudov Davronbek Ahrorjon o'g'li***Fergana State University, 3rd year student*

Abstract: The article discusses many modern pedagogical techniques for teaching foreign languages, their applications in lessons, and the relevance of effective method utilization in real-world situations. Additionally, specific details are provided regarding how these techniques might help pupils fully master a foreign language and become fluent speakers of that language.

Key words: method, English, efficiency, education, student, foreign language, ICT.

Introduction

Education of the young generation in the spirit of love and allegiance to the Motherland, national pride, high morality and spirituality, pride in our old and rich heritage, and national and international values is one of the most pressing concerns of our day. Fundamental changes to the global education system have made it more difficult to provide the right environment for students to study foreign languages effectively, communicate in a foreign language in all contexts, and improve their oral and writing communication skills in a foreign language. Organizations like UNESCO, UNICEF, the Association of European Universities, and the European Network for Quality Assurance in Higher Education address challenges relating to students' capacity to think in a foreign language, foster their intellectual development, and assess their readiness. growing. The evolution of this topic in general trends is crucial for modernity and the growth of foreign language

proficiency in the next generation, and it helps students' creative thinking skills in relation to issues with contemporary education. Coordination with educational initiatives that adhere to international standards and are based on foreign experiences became the cornerstone for enhancing the higher pedagogical education system as part of the reform of our nation's educational system. It is urgently necessary to fundamentally alter the quality of education on the basis of international experiences in Uzbekistan, taking into account native mentality and traditions. Therefore, foreign language classes are being held as a means of developing future employees for the higher education system of our republic and locating information required for scientific purposes, in order to read original literature in the specialty, in order to form the ability to participate in oral communication in a foreign language.

METHODS AND ANALYSIS OF THE LITERATURE.

Every person living in the Republic of Uzbekistan has a right to be able to read authentic works of literature written in languages other than his own, comprehend them, and use them in their line of work. He should also be able to freely discuss the subject with the interlocutor in a foreign language. After all, the current globalized era demands that people study foreign languages.

The education of foreign languages is given great consideration in our nation, which has the honor of being independent. The training of thousands of foreign language teachers, the creation of language rooms in contemporary educational institutions, the creation of multimedia textbooks in English, German, and French, and the preparation of electronic resources for English learning are all examples of how to create the conditions for personnel to advance their skills both domestically and abroad. The main objective is to establish the prerequisites for the growth of international cooperation and communication, the accomplishments of world civilization, and the utilization of global information resources by young

people. This is accomplished by educating the next generation in foreign languages and enhancing the training of professionals who can speak these languages fluently. ‘Those who know nothing of foreign languages know nothing of their own’ said J.W von Goethe. For this reason, learning foreign languages and freely sharing ideas in them is one of the most crucial jobs, not just for foreign language specialists but for all prospective employees studying in universities that do not specialize in languages. A person who speaks a foreign language will actually benefit from a variety of options. Today, great foreign language skills are one of the most important qualifications for employees.

In order to effectively train specialists in all disciplines, including the introduction of new technological methods for teaching foreign languages, it is crucial to prioritize the educational system. After all, language is a manifestation of all forms of connection between individuals, including spiritual communication.

The following priority areas for research on teaching foreign languages to students in higher education institutions that do not specialize in languages are being pursued worldwide: Enhancement of pedagogical methods for instructing pupils in foreign languages in accordance with the European CEFR; instructional technology; reinforcement of the objectivity of control; and organization of autonomous learning both within and outside of the classroom. The needs of society, as well as social norms, circumstances, and regulations, are used to determine the objectives of teaching a foreign language. The objectives of teaching foreign languages are influenced by the advancement and development of society. All foreign language teachers should outline their objectives in advance because teaching a foreign language in higher education has its own purposes. Since "the aims of foreign language instruction affect the content, means, methods, and principles of teaching," as scientists O'. Hoshimov and I. Yakubov wrote in the book "Methodology of

English Language Teaching," this is true. They can be classified into two groups based on the objectives and duties of teaching English in higher education institutions:

1. Institutions that develop experts in English as a foreign language include universities and faculties.
2. Institutions that offer foreign language education but do not train English specialists.

Since English language experts are trained in higher education institutions of the first group, the objectives of teaching English in these two groups are distinct, and as a result, English is taught in depth and in its whole, both theoretically and practically. A comprehensive goal of the English language is envisioned in the second group of educational institutions, i.e., those that are not philological. In order for the student to use English in his future speciality, it is important to teach him how to acquire a general education in the language. By acquiring the terminology associated with his area of expertise, he is taught to read and translate texts while also partially communicating in his line of work.

The following objectives guide foreign language instruction in higher education institutions: 1) practical or communicative, 2) general education, 3) education, and 4) application of the knowledge and abilities obtained, i.e. development yadi The implementation of the communication aim involves general educational, educational, and developmental goals. Let's examine these Four objectives in more detail:

1. Communicative (practical) goal: Students will be able to learn English through the achievement of this goal. The ability to independently use lexical and grammatical pronunciation materials in speech is a need for students. Skills in reading, writing, and speaking English are developed.

2. General educational goal: Through this goal, students' thinking will be further developed, they will be able to receive and give information in the English language, they will understand the language better, they will learn new things about the language, and they will learn more about the history and literature of the people who live in the country where the language is being studied. It is intended to do so at the expense of helping kids comprehend and learn about different cultures. Students' comprehension, thinking, and worldview are developed through the study of a foreign language.

3. Providing an international, moral, and artistic education as well as a work-ready mindset in English classes is the goal of this aim. Naturally, this is accomplished through studying English language resources in relation to the subject of English speaking and the substance of English documents.

4. The rules for getting to know children and kids personally are outlined in this developmental aim. It improves one's ability to analyze facts in a language, generalize, draw an autonomous conclusion, and speak and move. It develops independent preparation for extracurricular activities, their implementation, and teaches by imagining, creating a speech situation, having a logical connection in speech, being able to think independently, understanding the meaning of words, working independently with a dictionary, and participating in optional activities. The four objectives listed above are always complementary and connected. The information delivered, reviewed, and speaking exercises in each lesson should all work toward achieving these four objectives.

By the time they finish a higher education facility, students must be able to hear, comprehend, and communicate ideas both verbally and in writing in English. The amount of lesson hours is specified in the programs of higher education institutions that do not specialize in languages. Foreign languages are taught in educational

institutions other than philological ones using specialized curricula. Teachers in these special non-philological educational institutions who teach in the Uzbek language choose and use a variety of textbooks and manuals while taking into account the specifics of the field because programs and textbooks for such institutions are not yet available in English. One of the key concerns with methodology is the subject matter of the lessons. Currently, the nature and scope of knowledge, materials, exercises, and skills taught in foreign languages in higher education institutions that do not specialize in languages are viewed as being dictated by the objectives and tasks of the students' education. Two general requirements and their interconnectedness should not be overlooked while defining an educational subject's content:

1) The demand that we succeed or fail in achieving the objective we have established for the teaching content we have chosen; 2) This is the prerequisite for mastering or failing to master the teaching content we have chosen in our circumstances. These Two prerequisites can be used to decide the topic matter of the foreign language education course. The project of the higher education foreign language program determines the subject matter of English instruction. Every foreign language instructor is required to structure their lessons according to this program. The following are included by O'. Hoshimov and I. Yaqubov in their discussion of foreign language teaching approach at the moment.

1. Subject: (Thematic) reading and oral speech subjects.
2. Language resources (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar.)
3. lexical, grammatical, orthographic, and pronunciation skill formation and development;
4. speech skill formation, instruction, and development (listening, speaking, reading, writing skills).

5. Providing instruction on how to use supplementary books when studying the English language

The topic determines which texts are chosen. The core of the practical objective of teaching a foreign language is the acquisition of speaking abilities and activities. The purpose and what of teaching a foreign language are addressed in the course material.

The higher education institution has chosen language resources for foreign languages (English, German, and French) at this time. Achieving the goal will be considerably aided by carefully chosen information. The learning purpose informs and directs the choice of content. Speech samples are chosen along with language resources for choosing content. They form the cornerstone of speech instruction. The logical organization of instruction is taken into consideration when determining the subject. The conditions of education are related to the educational content. The size of the instructional content is also influenced by the goal of teaching a foreign language. It is meant to profoundly alter foreign language instruction in the current day. The following three conditions must be met.

3. Independent acquisition of a foreign language subject. 1. Increasing the scientific level of foreign language teaching and its practical orientation. 2. Strengthening the educational component of the foreign language subject.

There are two approaches to implement the first requirement. first way. altering the educational curriculum.

Reconstructing the methods for teaching foreign languages is a second option. Eliminating the ways and improving the education and training system is a reconstruction strategy that was once popular but is no longer effective in the modern world. Popularization of best practices and reconstruction of the methodology based on advancements in linguistics, psychology, pedagogy, and psycholinguistics are

key to raising the scientific level of foreign language methodology. Focusing the student's attention on autonomous work on a foreign language and abilities is required for foreign language teaching to go in a practical manner. By teaching relevant, educational texts, newspaper articles, assessing sociopolitical, educational concerns, identifying the main concept of the text, and carrying out higher education outside of the classroom, the educational component of the foreign language topic is increased and strengthened. They enhance pupils' perspectives on the globe and educate them in the values of friendship, internationalism, and patriotism.

Conclusion

Lessening the amount of content pupils are given and streamlining the learning process are other ways to adapt to the demands of the modern world. These are considered in the new foreign language curriculum. The teacher addresses the students in terms of practical material mastery for this reason. In order to increase kids' potential vocabulary, instruction is centered on helping children become proficient in both productive (speaking, writing expression) and receptive (listening, reading) language skills. Effective generalization and development of the teaching process form the cornerstone of a strong education. Optimization has gained popularity recently.

The capacity to find, select, and use a simple, convenient technique, manner, system, principle, instrument, or exercise that is appropriate for the context, conditions, higher education students and their selected fields, where a foreign language is being taught, is known as optimization. Due to the variations in class schedules and the effects of the students' mother tongues, optimization is specific to the different types of family educational institutions. The ability to provide information in a foreign language through speaking and writing, as well as to receive it through reading,

listening, and understanding, must be practiced during this current phase of communicative competence development.

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